

IN LEARNING THE SCIENCE OF HISTORY A.. ORINBOEV'S PHILOSOPHICAL CONCEPT

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Abstract:The article analyzes Urinboev's philosophical views in the study of history. Urinboev's research is related to the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid dynasty, the life and works of Alisher Navoi and Abdurahman Jami, as well as the development of the Naqshbandiya and Khojagon tariqahs. The study demonstrates how Urinboev's philosophical perspectives help understand the social and spiritual significance of historical figures, integrate science and spirituality, and analyze financial and social relations.

Keywords:History, Urinboev, philosophical views, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Abdurahman Jami, spirituality, social life, historical research.

A philosophical approach is of great importance in the study of history. It allows us to analyze historical events not only as a set of facts, but also their spiritual, social, and economic consequences. From this point of view, Urinbayev's scientific work is significant as a practical example of philosophical views in historiography.

Urinbayev's research is related to the era of Amir Temur and the Temurids, the life and creative legacy of Alisher Navoi and Abdurakhmon Jami, as well as the history of the Naqshbandi and Khojagon orders, and is not limited to rewriting scientific facts. In his opinion, one of the main tasks of historical science is to understand the social, spiritual and philosophical significance of historical figures and events and draw conclusions from them.

By analyzing Orinboev's philosophical views formed through historical research, their impact on science, spirituality and social life, the essence of medieval manuscripts is studied.

A. Orinboev's philosophical views are reflected in his scientific, cultural and social activities. His thoughts are mainly expressed in the following aspects:

1. Urinbayev emphasizes the importance of historical knowledge in the spiritual and social development of humanity through the activities of historical figures, in particular Amir Temur and Alisher Navoi. In his opinion, history is not just a record of facts, but a means of teaching moral and spiritual lessons, serving as an experience and example for future generations.

2. Urinbayev emphasizes that behind each historical event and the activities of a person there are various social, economic and cultural reasons. Therefore, when studying history, it is necessary to analyze not only the occurrence of events, but also their impact on human life, society and the development of the state. For example, Amir Temur's activities in state administration and organization of society played an important role in the formation of national and cultural heritage.

3. Also, through the literary and spiritual heritage of Alisher Navoi, Urinbayev teaches the importance of history in human spirituality and cultural development. In Navoi's work, humanism, morality, and spiritual values are practically demonstrated through historical events. This allows historical analysis to be not limited to facts, but also to study their spiritual and moral impact.

4. At the same time, Urinbayev sees history and cultural heritage as an important factor in strengthening the spiritual foundation of society and educating future generations. In his opinion, through historical knowledge, people are able to feel social responsibility, preserve spiritual values, and develop cultural heritage.

5. The harmony of science and spirituality - In his research, Alisher Navoi and Abdurakhmon Jomi put forward the view that science and spirituality

should support each other. He emphasizes that the spiritual development of a person is connected with his activity and social responsibility.

6. Spiritual leadership and social responsibility. Urinbayev's research examines historical figures as people who were active in government and social life. In his opinion, a truly philosophical person should uphold spiritual values and work for social justice and peace.

7. Philosophical approach to financial and economic issues. In studying the system of trade and lending, he paid attention not only to the economic aspect, but also to its moral and philosophical aspects. He analyzes the social consequences of usury and interest-bearing loans, showing their impact on fair financial relations.

Conclusion: A. Urinbayev's philosophical views are to combine historical knowledge with spiritual value and social responsibility, to develop science and spirituality, and to evaluate financial relations on a moral basis. His ideas serve as the basis for combining historiography and economic philosophy in modern Uzbekistan.

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